

**STUDY ON THE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCIES OF
STUDENTS LEARNING KOREAN AS A SECOND FOREIGN
LANGUAGE (based on the curriculum of Korean as a foreign language)**

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Abstract. This article examines the communicative competencies of students learning Korean as a second foreign language, adopted by the Ministry of Education of Republic of Korea. In the curriculum, communication skills (oral production) are included in the category of production activities, which at the same time has a subcategory of writing production. The article examines in detail all subcategories of production category and gives them a definition.

Key words: competency, oral production, written production, the curriculum, Korean as second foreign language, language activities.

This article examines the communicative (oral) competencies of students learning Korean as a second foreign language, adopted by the Ministry of Education of Republic of Korea. In the curriculum, communication skills (oral production) are included in the category of production activities, which at the same time has a subcategory of writing production. The article examines in detail all subcategories of production category and gives them a definition.

Generally, the content system of language activities was organized into two categories, communicative language activities and communicative language strategies, as upper categories. Among these, four categories, including *reception, production, mediation, and interaction*, were set and organized as subcategories of communicative language activities. This article examines the production category, which combines speaking and writing.

Production is a category that has replaced the traditional term *expression*. The production category described details with a focus on the process of creating and outputting language to convey opinions, intentions, and emotions to the other party. Production skills are acquired through learning and experience, and production strategies are used to refine production. In production activities, fluency and

accuracy of production are emphasized, especially fixed formality must be maintained when producing in formal situations or specific genres.

Based on the curriculum of Korean as a foreign language adopted by the Ministry of Education of Republic of Korea [1, 25] in 2021, the production category is divided into production activities and production strategies as shown in [Figure 1], and the entire production category is composed of a total of 12 sub-areas as follows.

[Figure 1] Structure of production categories

The production category presented competency statements that specifically considered three aspects: topic, discourse type, and background knowledge. Since the Uzbek education system for a second foreign language considers the basic level that need to be mastered, this article will also consider all the competencies of students at levels A1 and A2.

Overall spoken production	
A2+	Same as A2
A2	Can talk about very close people or about daily life. (e.g. classmates, weekend family trips, school life, academic-related areas, etc.) Can speak in simple phrases and sentences.
A1	Can talk about very close people and familiar places. Can only speak with a few simple phrases and expressions. (Example: Greeting expressions such as ‘Hello?’ ‘Thank you.’) Can speak key vocabulary related to school subjects. (e.g. math, history/geography, science vocabulary)
Pre A1	Can tell basic information about him/herself. (e.g. name, address, family, nationality) Able to speak only with basic vocabulary, a few simple phrases, and typical expressions. (Example: ‘Hello?’, ‘Goodbye.’, ‘Hi.’, ‘Bye.’, ‘I’m sorry.’, etc.)

In the spoken language production category, an explanation of the overall spoken production category was provided so that one can understand the overall performance and production ability encompassing all subcategories. In this curriculum, oral production is roughly divided into sustained monologues, public announcements, and addressing audiences. Sustained monologues include describing experiences, giving information, logical argument (putting a case).

Now we will consider the competencies of students for each subcategory.

Describing experience	
A2+	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Can briefly explain things and habits experienced in daily life or school life. (e.g. parties with friends, life outside of school, classroom situations) · Can talk about one’s plans. · Can explain special days. (e.g. how to celebrate Christmas) · Can explain school life. (e.g. school routine, school events, school rules)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Subject contents can be explained using subject-related terms. (e.g. math problems, science experiments) by referring to the textbook. · Can explain simple scientific experiment procedures. · Can briefly summarize the contents of a poem or story and express one's impressions of it.
A2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Can explain one's educational background, occupation, and living conditions. (Example: educational background, means of transportation used to go to school from home) · Can describe family and friends. (e.g. parent's occupation, friend's appearance) · Can talk about what he/she did or did on weekends or holidays. · Can talk about what one's good at and what you are not good at in school. (Example: Sports one's good at, sports one's not good at)
A1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Can tell basic information about him/herself. (e.g. name, hometown, school attended, work done) After preparing in advance, can talk about things related to his/her daily life. (e.g. likes and dislikes, things he/her often do with friends, family members) · Can express feelings using simple vocabulary along with gestures. (Example: '(Make a circle sign by putting thumb and index finger together) Okay, I understand.')
Pre A1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · After preparing in advance, can tell basic information about himself using typical expressions. (Example: Name ('저는○○예요./○이예요.'), age, country, address, phone number) · Can express your feelings using simple vocabulary along with gestures.

Describing experiences is the ability to tell stories or explain things, and it refers to the ability to describe oneself or familiar people, or to describe experiences and feelings about daily life and school life

In addition, since the curriculum of Korean as a foreign language adopted by the Ministry of Education of Republic of Korea views learners as social agents, the situations in which spoken language production takes place are concrete real-life

situations, that is, conversation situations where one speaks directly to the other party (e.g., providing information) and announcement or presentation situations where one speaks to a large number of people (e.g. : Presentation).

	Providing information	Giving a presentation
A2+	Same as A2	If prepare in advance, he or she can present on topics related to daily life. (e.g. opinions, plans, actions and reasons for doing so) After the presentation, he or she can answer questions from the audience.
A2	Can use vocabulary related to sequential expressions (e.g., turn right, just before, first, next) to describe how to get to a specific place.	If prepare in advance, he or she can present on a familiar topic. (e.g. country, athletic team) After the presentation, he or she may repeat explanations at the audience's request or provide standardized answers to audience questions.
A1	After preparing in advance, can briefly describe specific objects or pictures using basic vocabulary, phrases, and typical expressions. Can present basic information related to school classes. (e.g. classroom size, number of girls/boys, favorite subject)	If prepare in advance, he or she can read short sentences. (e.g. school introduction, short presentation assignment, etc.)
Pre A1	No ability statement	No ability statement

In this curriculum, considering elementary and middle school learners, in addition to the seven grades of Pre-A1, A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, and C2 set in the Common European Reference Standard (2020), the plus grade of A2+ , B1+, and B2+ are additionally set, but in the calculation category, the plus grade ability description may or may not be the same as A2, B1, or B2.

As can be seen from the following, the ability descriptions of A2 and A2+ are the same in making announcements (<oral production<production activities).

	Making a logical argument	Announcing
A2+	Can reveal one's preferences (likes, dislikes) and compare and present the reasons.	Same as A2
A2	If the listener waits, he or she can present his or her opinion.	After preparing in advance, can announce information about his/her daily life and school life briefly and simply so that the other person can understand. (e.g. class times, classroom location, etc.)
A1	No ability statement	No ability statement
Pre A1	No ability statement	No ability statement

Next, the written language production categories are explained as follows.

First, in the written production category, an explanation of the overall written production category was provided so that the overall written production ability encompassing all subcategories could be known. In this curriculum, written language production is divided into creative writing and academic writing (written reports and essays).

Creative writing is the ability to write various types of texts using personal and creative expression, more specifically about school classes, school life (school activities, relationships with friends), and cultural events (plays, movies, concerts).

It refers to the ability to write or express a critical review of a literary work in a detailed, structured text. For each level of creative writing skills, competency statements were used based on the complexity of discourse ranging from words to phrases, clauses, sentences, and texts. Because adolescent learners have relatively more difficulties with written language production activities than with oral language production activities, only grades from A1 to C1 were described.

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